

ISic0340

Funerary inscription for Lucius Cassius Hermes

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017.03.20

Last Change

2017-07-11 - Jonathan Prag added additional metadata and edited the text

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 568

Physical Description

A rectangular marble plaque, intact on all sides (minor chipping to the lower edge), finished on the reverse.

Dimensions

Height 37 cm
Width 27.5 cm
Depth 2.8 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-7: 24-31 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: Not measured mm

Text

1. D (is) · M (anibus) · s (acrum) ·
2. L (ucius) · Cassius
3. Hermes ·
4. optimus ·
5. virorum ·
6. vix (it) · ann (is) · LX
7. IIII · f (ilii) · p (osuerunt) · p (atri) · m (erenti) ·

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Sacred to the spirits of the underworld. Lucius Cassius Hermes, best of men, lived for 60 years. His

four children set this up for a deserving father.

Translation (it)

Consacrato agli Dei Mani, Lucio Cassio Hermes, ottimo tra gli uomini, visse 60
anni. I quattro figli
posero per il padre meritevole.

Commentary

The deceased is a Roman citizen. The Greek cognomen, 'Hermes' suggests that he or one of his ancestors was either a Greek Sicilian or a freed slave. The phrase *optimus virorum* is unusual and so is the last line: abbreviations are very common in Latin epigraphy, but they are not always easy to resolve - epigraphers solve them by comparing with other texts, but this does not have an exact parallel.

This inscription was found in or near the same tomb as ISic0378. The style of the inscriptions is similar, but the form of the letters is not identical, and the texts were engraved by different people. They could be approximately contemporary. It is impossible to know if Tyche and Hermes were related.

Digital identifiers:

TM 491549

EDR 139407

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7056 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650759>)

Korhonen, K. 2004. *Le iscrizioni del Museo civico di Catania : storia delle collezioni, cultura epigrafica, edizione.* Helsinki. At 66

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